

COMMUNITY BEHAVIOUR AND PERFORMANCE OF DEVELOPMENTAL AGENCIES: THE CASE OF NIGER DELTA DEVELOPMENT COMMISSION IN NIGERIA

¹Roland Ufuoma Ejedegba, Ph.D.

Faculty of the Social Sciences,
Department of Economics,
Delta State University, Abraka,
Delta State, Nigeria.

Email: rejedegba@gmail.com; rolegba@yahoo.com

²Alazigha Woyengibaragha

Leeds Beckett University, Leeds, Uk.

Email: messesse@yahoo.co.uk

Corresponding Author: ¹Roland Ufuoma Ejedegba, Ph.D.

Email: rejedegba@gmail.com

Abstract

This study examines the host community behaviour and the challenges they pose to developmental agency (NDDC) on sustainable development of the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. Data for the study was generated through structured interview. The study reveals that illicit financial gains of community members, poor communication, lack of transparency from NDDC and their contractors, youth restiveness, intra/inter community conflicts affect the implementation of developmental projects. Lack of awareness of NDDC project initiation and implementation plans cause conflict in the region. The paper, stresses that when articulating future developmental plans, NDDC should consider inputs by local oil bearing communities.

Keywords: Development; Agencies; Community Behaviour; Conflict; Niger Delta Region.

Introduction

The agitation of the people of Niger Delta for special attention pre-dates 1960 when Nigeria attained independence from Britain. These agitations which started as a result of the peculiar marshy topography of the region were worsened by rapid degradation of the environment due to oil exploration and exploitation activities over the past decades. Expanse of land used for subsistence farming by a good percentage of the people has been acquired or polluted. Fishing which is a prominent occupation of majority of the rural dwellers has been severely impacted due to degraded marine ecology, thus negatively affecting their means of livelihood. The inability of the government to effectively address these issues has resulted in divergent characteristic behaviour.

In a bid to address the agony of the people, government had over the years put strategies in place to develop the Region by creating special agencies and institutions ranging from the Wilinks Commission, River Basin Development Authorities, the defunct Oil Mineral Producing Areas Development Commission (OMPADEC) and Ministry of Niger Delta Affairs and the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) with specific mandates. Studies have established that the Niger Delta has wholesomely experienced challenges due to oil exploration activities. In most cases, youths are being used as sustaining engines or tools to ferment trouble in the region (Erega and Irughe, 2009). In the same vein, Ekpeyong (2007) noted that crises appear to be the primary or dominant issue among host communities across Africa in the course of scrambling for fair portion of wealth from the extractive industry. Indeed, Kalaya (2006) and Nareke (2009) separately remarked that the spate of youth restiveness in the Niger-Delta may undermine development effort of government at transforming both human and physical infrastructures in the region, based on the perceived effect it has on the communal participation and harmonious working relationship with development institutions.

Youth restiveness in the Niger Delta Region over the years include incessant protest/agitations against developers/government; abrupt work stoppage; seizure of working tools of developers , thereby incapacitating the developers; vandalization of equipments at site; kidnapping of oil workers or developers and bombing of oil installations. All these are caused by lack of understanding between stakeholders-Government, Multinational companies and Community people in the oil rich region.

Several reasons have been advanced for the youth restiveness which include poor working relations between the communities and developmental agencies; undermined social integration, for instance, no input from the communities while articulating policies affecting the environment/region; poor discharge of corporate social responsibility on the part of the agencies; youth seeing violence as a means or best strategy for expressing their frustration/aggression and consider compensation of degraded communities as inadequate. Indeed, most of the complaint of the youth relate to unemployment, environmental degradation, destruction of means of livelihood and health hazards.

Companies have always failed to keep to the terms of understanding/agreement reached with their host communities. Government and political class often fail to address the

politics of oil thus leading to inevitable various crime commissions. Community participation is an aura igniting phenomenon that makes community members feel 'psychologically reinforced' and therefore be willing to be at their best for their common good (Bira, 2010).

Exploration and exploitation of natural endowments the world over, have no doubt created the premise for multiple actions and activities that are either functional to the overall development agenda or inimical to the achievement of strategic development effort of all stakeholders. Ibaba (2005), working on oil mining activities and associated conflicts, argued that the attitude of not being holistic in the activities that precede mining is the reason for during mining and post mining conflicts that have impeded the desired rate of development that ordinarily should accompany exploration and exploitation of resources.

Governments over the years have created special agencies and institutions with the primary goal of speeding up development of the Niger Delta. Notwithstanding, these efforts and evidence of project implementation in some of these communities, relationship between the host communities, oil exploration firms, and development agencies seems to be far from improving. The region continues to witness crisis, increasing tension, and the demand for development seems far from being addressed. This increasing tension, cry for recognition and seemingly deteriorating physical environment as well as social changes in the Niger Delta communities may pose further developmental challenges not only to the Niger Delta region but the country at large. Indeed, these developmental challenges constitute major motivation for this research.

Crisis in the region are perceived to be on community youth restiveness; financial demand of community members on developmental agencies/project contractors; inter and intra-community conflicts emanating from awarded project. All these issues are interrelated and intertwined, causing endless conflict in the region.

The aim of this study is to explore the impact of community behaviour on the performance of developmental institutions in the Niger Delta Region. The case institution explored is the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) which was established by the Federal Government to fast track the development of the Region.

Specifically, the study is set to determine issues that affect the development effort of the NDDC in the Niger Delta Region. These are financial demands by community members from contractors; community youth restiveness; lack of awareness of project benefits by the community members; intra/inter communal conflicts and, corruption and lack of transparency in project design and implementation.

Although several scholars, including Unongo, (2008); Jaja, (2006) have examined the impact of oil exploration on environmental degradation and livelihood of host communities, not much attention has been paid to community behavioural contents and context toward the developmental agencies as well as the consequences on project implementation/community development.

The Study Area

The Niger Delta is a tropical rainforest with a robust ecology comprising of a wide range of plants and animals both aquatic and terrestrial species. The Niger Delta region of Nigeria consists of the following nine states: Abia, Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, Ondo, Imo and Rivers. The region has witnessed a number of attempts to influence the pace and nature of development in the area and improve the standard of life for its people. The very first attempt made at developing the region was by the Sir Henry Willink's Commission of (1958) which recommended that the area deserves special developmental attention by the federal government of Nigeria. In response to this, the federal government established the Niger Delta Development Board (NDDDB) in 1960 to manage the developmental needs and challenges of the region. It lasted for seven years and achieved little before it faded away following the military coup of 1966 in Nigeria and the outbreak of civil war in 1967, (NDDC, 2006). Following growing agitation for a renewed focus on the development of the region, the 1979/83 Administration of Alhaji Shehu Usman Aliyu Shagari set up a Presidential Task Force (popularly known as the 1.5% Committee) in 1980 and 1.5% of the federation account was allocated to the Committee to tackle the developmental problems of the region. This committee subsequently was also seen to be ineffective since only a few projects were shown compared to the funding received. This Committee for this and other reasons was short-lived. To further ameliorate the discontent and restiveness of the people of the Niger Delta Region, government set up another commission, the Oil and Mineral Producing Areas Development Commission

(OMPADEC) in 1992. Although OMPADEC completed several projects, it also recorded numerous abandoned projects coupled with huge outstanding debts. The collapse of OMPADEC heralded the creation of the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) in 2000.

The important projects and programmes preceding the creation of the NDDC suffered from lack of clarity of vision, adherence to meaningful, achievable goals and objectives within the framework of programmes and projects execution. Failures of successive programmes to reach out to the communities have served to compound the frustrations of the people of the Niger Delta. An open and transparent relationship between NDDC, Federal Government, States and Local Government, private sector organizations (including the oil industry), communities and civil society as main actors and stakeholders is perceived to be a panacea for achieving the goals of government in its bid to develop the Niger Delta area.

Theoretical Frameworks

Frustration-Aggression Theory: The theory views conflict from the human psychological perspective and blames conflict on the inability of the human species to attain a set goal. The theory posits that there is a gap between what people feel they want or deserve and what they actually get which results to frustration that culminates in aggression and violence. In a broader dimension, conflict is attributed to frustration arising from unresolved challenges or obstacles, suggesting that conflict will always occur as long as challenges are not resolved. Indeed, Ibaba (2011) has noted that the conflicts in the communities of the Niger Delta Region are triggered by several factors adduced to the inhibition of goal attainment such as centralized federalism and inequitable distribution of oil revenue arising from ethnic-based political domination and neglect of the region's development; oil induced environmental degradation, loss of income and increased poverty, corruption in governance and poor service delivery, as well as the inefficient implementation of corporate social responsibility by multinational corporation (MNC) and their refusal to pay adequate compensation for damages to properties caused by oil production activities.

The Greed and Grievance Theory – In studying the causes of war in resource rich African countries, Collier and Hoeffler (2004) developed a model to explain the reason for conflict in some African countries with natural resource endowment. For them,

conflict in those areas leading to war in most cases are driven by the desire to take more than one deserves (greed) and/or to take out vengeance on the unjust system or for past injustices suffered. In essence, fear of, and response to domination and deprivation are the driving forces for practically all major conflicts propelling the spiral of crisis.

Another theoretical study that relate to conflict, is that posited by Auty, 1993. This study explains why resource-rich countries tend to spawn predatory political States that distort the economy, creating growth collapse, low educational attainment, a large cohort of unemployed young males and high resource dependence. In addition, the study identifies the specific properties of natural resources associated with conflict. However, this manifestation of the, resource curse, like others, is not a deterministic phenomenon so that domestic and global policies can limit resource-driven conflict.

Community Participation Theories

Human Right-Based Approach

In this study, Human Right-Based Approach (HRBA) is considered an important framework that will guide theoretical discourse on community behaviour and performance of development institutions like the NDDC. It permits communities' participation in decisions regarding the impact of oil exploration and exploitation and other extractive resources on their livelihood. The underlying belief is that development is based on rights and obligations which are owed in a social relationship that exist between mining firms and communities where the resources are naturally found, Echave, *et al.*(2008). In line with this, there is need for concrete awareness and active community participation in order to maximize the performance of developmental institutions.

Social Exchange Theory

Social exchange according to Wajda and Angela (2012) involves a series of interdependent collaborations that are, subject to the activities of the other partner in the social relationship. These authors noted that an exchange begins with one party giving something of benefit or valued resource to another while expecting the other to reciprocate. The Niger Delta communities in this case are seen to have allowed the tapping of their natural resource crude-oil from their domain and this comes with attendant degradation of the environment in a momentous scale.

Host communities to multinational oil exploring and exploiting firms expectedly have a relationship that also extends to the formally created development institution and of course this social relationship rest on reciprocity (Gouldner, 1960). The NDDC has clear-cut expectation from the communities they are expected to strategically develop. While the communities expect such degree of cooperation to facilitate development, the commission which is a development type should equally show reciprocity by giving adequate attention to initiating and completing projects for them. The potency of the relationship towards yielding the desired goal is essentially premised on the dosage of mutual trust and respect for each other's obligations.

Human Capital Theory

The human capital theory was theorized by Lohrentz (2006), as the basis for many development efforts of the 1990's in the United States. Human capital theory proposes an approach that takes into consideration the needs of the people in an organization which in this instance is the personnel of government development institution and the needs of the people of the region. It brings to the fore the facts that individuals have their needs and aspirations therefore, emphasis should be on how to acquire requisite skills that improves their capabilities. The people of the Niger Delta have had a setback in terms of human capital development and this is among the core reasons for agitation. It is imperative therefore, that any institution created to foster development should take human capital as a critical need of the people and thus require strategic attention. The Board, management and staff of the institution would require the needed skills to equitably implement the development plans and effectively manage any conflict arising from their activities in the host communities.

Community Development

While the literature on the definition of community is subtly variegated, it does not erase the fact that community asserts relationships and networks with people of common characteristics and in most times common vision. It conveys tradition and patterns of behaviour. Folahon (2005) views community development in the light of communal aspirations with a vision to improve on the overall activities that make for their wellbeing. The aspirations, in Folahon's view instigate social change that culminates to multiple actions which are development targeted.

The achievement of effective community participation requires empowering local people to be adequately represented and directly involved in development initiation and implementation. In addition, there is need for effective mobilization, consultation and collaboration between the community, development agencies and government. This direct collaboration creates confidence and could serve as the bases for traditional institutions, community development committees, youth and women representatives to advocate and convince the citizens for behavioural change that could attract improved infrastructural development.

Method

The philosophical stance adopted is quantitative (deductive) research method in the positivism domain. It is an exploratory design. The structured interview (questionnaire) process was guided by the research ethics.

Sampling Strategy

The study is based on survey data collected from community members where NDDC project is on-going. *Sampling frame* for the selection of these communities was from NDDC list of communities with on-going projects. Non-probability sampling frame was adopted. The sampling frame from NDDC based on random numbering could not work because, the NDDC list of communities mixed places where projects are already going on with communities where projects are still at the proposal stage. Consequently, it was difficult to differentiate communities with on-going project from those without on-going projects. This forced the study to adopt purposeful selection of communities for the investigation.

Before the selection of communities, the NDDC states list (where NDDC covers) serves as the sampling frame for selection of the state. Probability sampling was adopted for the state by random selection from the list of states that constitute the Niger Delta Development States. The states that emerge for the investigation include: Delta, Edo and Bayelsa. From these states, the following communities as contain in Table 1 were purposefully selected for the investigation showing the number of respondents per state.

The 1996 population census of Nigeria projection was used to select the population and sample size. The choice of population Census of 1996 was because the 2006 population

census does not provide census figures per enumeration areas but summed all the communities in the local government areas (LGA). Using 2006 census figure by Local Government Area (LGA) will provide a distorted population size and spatial difference. More than 50 towns and sometimes different ethnic groups may be in one LGA. Also, the projects were community based as well as the study focus.

Table 1: Selected States, Communities, Population and Sample Size

State and Communities	Population Census (1996)	Sample Size (Respondents)	Percentage of Sample to Population
Delta State			
1. Oko-Odifulu	325	177	54.46%
2. Ubeji	706	116	16.43%
3. Egbokodo	290	54	18.62
4. Ibusa	2166	159	7.20%
5. Isselle-Asagba	3284	86	2.61%
6. Okpanam	5158	217	4.20%
Edo State			
1. Adolor	1678	349	20.79%
2. Uromi	8119	295	3.63%
3. Umu-Ubeh	576	31	5.38%
4. Agbede	4238	238	5.52%
Bayelsa State			
1. Okoloba	385	273	70.91%
Total	26,925	1,995	7.40%

Source: Author's Construction, 2017.

A total population of 26,925 represents the study area while 7.4% of the population was covered (1,995) – which may be considered a fair and representative sample size.

The sample for the study is carefully chosen to ensure that it is made up of all the vital elements of the population that will provide the relevant data. On the side of the development commission, it is made up of the state directors from the three selected states: Delta, Edo and Bayelsa.

Instruments and Measures

The instruments used for the study was self-administered structured interview. The dimension of Community behaviour based on illicit financial demand, youth restiveness, intra/inter community conflict and community participation/awareness were measured with already established instruments estimating well-known factors of the construct but with modifications to suit the study. A five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly

agree; 2 = Agree; 3 = Disagree, 4 = strongly disagree and 5 = Do not Know) was used for all items in the instrument.

Measurement of Independent Variables

Illicit financial demand was measured through seven substances adopted from an instrument developed by Barivure (2000). Respondents were asked to indicate their opinions on an item such as: ‘communities are more interested in money instead of quality of work’.

Youth restiveness was measured using seven items adopted from an instrument developed by Phil and Nancy (2007). Each respondent was asked to indicate his/her opinions on the items provided on the questionnaire. For example, ‘youths always disturb workmen on site’.

Community participation/awareness was assessed using eight items adopted from an instrument developed by Ayinla (2009). The respondents were asked to report their responses on an item such as: ‘I like community’s willingness to give support to projects because they know about them’.

Intra/inter community conflict was measured using five items adopted from an instrument developed by Ben and Meyo (2006). Respondents were asked to indicate their opinions on items such as: ‘contractors abandon sites because of intra/inter communal conflicts’.

Measurement of Dependent Variable

Performance of the development agency (NDDC) which comprised of poor quality of work, project abandonment and prolonged project completion were measured with already established instruments measuring identified factors of the construct but with modifications to suit the study.

Data Management

Analysis began with coding of the instruments. Then data was checked, formatted, recorded and labelled using a Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) adopted for Windows version 23. The rating scale was a five-point Likert scale. All values had

to be discrete values of 1, 2, 3, 4, or 5 and decimal points corrected to nearest unit. This scale is practically interesting and does not have a midpoint and, in that sense, forces a choice (Okolo, 2014). The five-point Likert scale was adopted in expectation of respondents' likelihood to score the midpoint.

To take care of missing values in the data set, a series mean value replacement was run using the SPSS programme. A number of missing data techniques are in use such as series mean value replacement, pair wise deletion, list wise deletion, similar response pattern imputation, and maximum likelihood estimation. In this study, missing values (maximum 2.5%) were replaced using the series means. With the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) at less than 2 and tolerance statistics above .90, it indicates that there was no co-linearity within the data showing that the items were distinct for the constructs under measurement.

Analysis of Data

The tests were conducted in two stages: Stage one involved descriptive statistics, and reliability tests. Descriptive statistics included computations of frequencies and percentages. The reliability test measures include Cronbach's alpha, split-half reliability, test-retest reliability, and inter-rater reliability, demonstrating different meanings of reliability. Cronbach's alpha is the commonest form of reliability coefficient (Garson, 2005), which was used in this study.

Stage two involved computing the zero-order correlations, and regressions. Using the SPSS version 17 adopted for windows, the Pearson zero-order correlations between the study variables were automatically obtained with either one or five per cent level of significance. The multiple regressions were also computed to establish the predictive powers of the independent variables on the dependent variables under study (Okolo, 2014).

Multivariate Regression Model Specification

To explore the empirical relationship between NDCC community development project performance (dependent variable) and the independent variables; transparency of NDCC project development/design and implementation, project benefits and Attitude to financial gains, illicit financial demand of community leaders and Intra/Inter community

conflicts as they affect NDDC project performance, the following model is functionally specified:

$$\text{Perf} = f(\text{ProjDev}, \text{ProjBen}, \text{Intra/Inter}, \text{IFG}) \dots \dots \dots (3.1)$$

$$\text{Perf} = \alpha_0 \text{ProjDev} + \alpha_1 \text{ProjBen} + \alpha_2 \text{Intra/Inter} + \alpha_3 \text{IFG} + U \dots \dots \dots (3.2)$$

Where $\alpha_0 - \alpha_3 > 0$, (a priori expectation)

and

ProjDev=Indices of Transparency of NDDC in Project Development/Design and Implementation.

ProjBen=Vector of Project Benefits and Attitude of Community leaders towards Financial Gains

Intra/Inter=Vector of the impact of Intra/Inter Community Conflicts on NDDC Development Projects

IFG = Vector of illicit financial demand of community leaders.

Perf= Vector of NDDC Community Development Project Outcomes/Performance

U= Stochastic term(disturbance term).

Result

Table 2: Correlation Matrix of the major Constructs

Variables		ProjDev	ProjBen	IntraInter	Perf
ProjDev	Pearson Correlation	1	.670**	.662**	.609**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	1995	1995	1995	1995
ProjBen	Pearson Correlation	.670**	1	.874**	.643**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	1995	1995	1995	1995
IntraInter	Pearson Correlation	.662**	.874**	1	.697**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	1995	1995	1995	1995
Perf	Pearson Correlation	.609**	.643**	.697**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	1995	1995	1995	1995

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Author's Construction, 2017.

Table 2 presents the correlation matrix of the major variables constructed in the model. The table reveals that there is positive relationship between the dependent variable, performance of the NDDC Community development projects and all the constructed independent variables which include transparency of NDDC project development/design and implementation, project benefits and Attitude to financial gains and Intra/Inter community conflicts as they affect NDDC project performance. A cursory look at the Table 2 reveals that intra /inter community conflicts as it affect

NDDC development projects is highly associated with perceived project benefits and the attitude of the community leaders (politicians, elders and youths) towards financial gains. This is indeed more informative given the correlation coefficient of determination of 0.874.

Table 3: Parameter Estimates: Multivariate Regression

Dependent Variable: Perf

Model	Coefficients		Coefficients	t.Stat.	Level of Significance.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.767	.124		14.217	.000
ProjDev	.240	.021	.250	11.603	.000
ProjBen	.204	.073	.182	2.780	.005
IntraInter	.488	.035	.443	13.985	.000
IFG	-.093	.058	-.089	-1.598	.110

Source: Author's computation, 2017.

Table 3 presents the outcome of the multivariate regression of the model that considers the relationship existing between the constructed socio-economic variables of interest in this study. The Table 3 provides evidence of transparency of NDDC as an agency of government in project development/design and implementation for community development. Project benefits and attitude of Community leaders towards Financial Gains as well as Intra/Inter community conflicts have positive and statistically significant relationship with NDDC community development project poor outcomes/performance. On the contrary to a priori expectation, the thematic variable of illicit financial demand of community leaders presents a negative outcome with low coefficient of -0.098 and statistically insignificant to explain variation in the performance of NDDC developmental projects.

Also, a cursory look at the regression results reveal that the variable of intra/inter community conflict impact significantly on NDDC community development project performance given the standardized coefficient of 0.49 as against the other variables with the maximum standardized coefficient of 0.24. Thus, the variable of intra/inter community conflicts is more informative in explaining variations in NDDC community development projects performance in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. This outcome is corroborated by the empirical evidence in Belam, (2007) in the work titled 'organizational Development: Changing the way we manage'. In that work, it was found that the presence of intra/inter communal conflict instil a sense of operational

caution thereby leading to either delayed job execution or poor quality of projects which may not align with development objectives.

Discussion of Results

Quantitatively, from the appendix, Table 4.1 reveals that 64% are of the opinion that community leader's involvement in illicit financial gains results in poor project implementation. While only 257 respondents representing 12.4% had contrary opinions. This shows the relationship between illicit financial demand and performance of NDDC. Table 4.2 however reveals that it cannot be concluded that community leaders' involvement in illicit financial gains result in poor monitoring of contractors. Consistent demand for financial gains from the contractors and community members also impede the performance of developmental institutions such as NDDC. Youth restiveness is not the proximate cause of project abandonment by NDDC as revealed in Table 4.15

The findings in Table 4.3 show 67% of the respondents affirmed that community representatives are not involved in the planning and execution of developmental projects initiated by NDDC, while 33% of the respondents are of the contrary. This position is corroborated where 1331 representing of respondents indicated 'No' that youth and elders of communities are not represented in all the process of project conception of NDDC. The findings in Table 4.4 and 4.5 further reveal the low level of awareness of community members in the citing and implementation of NDDC projects in the communities. These findings thus reveal that community participation and awareness is low. As such, the performance of NDDC in project design and execution will be faced with some form negative behaviour from the community members since they feel alienated. The feeling of alienation has the potential of triggering resistance and aggression towards NDDC. Such instances have contributed in youth restiveness. Estimates from the regression analysis reveal that intra/inter community conflict impact NDDC community development project performance given the standardized coefficient of 0.49 as against the other variables with the maximum standardized coefficient of 0.26. The variable of intra/inter community conflicts is more informative in explaining variations in NDDC community development projects in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria.

In the light of the debilitating effect of intra/inter communities conflicts on the performance of NDDC in the region, and the imperative of adequate positioning to withstand possible conflict in the future, communities must brace up to the challenge of ensuring cohesive relationship with each other by developing measures that identify and adequately manage key community based leadership structure, e.g. head of CDC, Youth and Women group, Vigilante/security group etc. There should be improved communication/transparency within and between communities. Besides, there should be concerted implementation of awareness campaign/sensitization of organised youth and women group on the negative impact of conflict/violence as a means of expressing frustration/aggression. Organising intra /inter communities games for social interaction such as Football matches, cultural dancing competitions could also help the host communities to be more cohesive in their relations with each other.

Conclusions

Conflict between developmental agencies, the government, multinational corporations and oil bearing communities has been the factors militating against the sustainable development of the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. It has resulted in exacerbating poverty, unemployment, and insecurity of life and property. The factors that have spurred conflict over the years include exclusion of local oil bearing communities in community social responsibility programmes and projects, lack of commitment on the part of government and its agencies alongside the oil firms in the discharge of their corporate social responsibility. Therefore, considering that community behaviour plays significant role in the performance of NDDC through creation of peaceful coexistence within and between communities in the region, it is imperative that government and its agencies alongside the oil companies operating in the region should discharge their social responsibility to the oil producing (Host) communities and get more involved in both human and physical development of the area in order to win the confidence of the people of the region. Stakeholders should intensify efforts to maintain the peaceful coexistence in the region while host communities should be much more cohesive in their relation with one another as this would generate inclusiveness and accommodation. When articulating future developmental plans, NDDC should consider inputs by local oil bearing communities. In particular, NDDC should involve and take

along the people of the host community in its community social responsibility programmes and projects. The felt need of the people should be done with the people involved in its planning, execution and evaluation stages. This would reduce friction between the stakeholders and would ultimately reduce conflict in the area. Failure in this regard, can make the community youths and elders feel alienated and neglected with potentials for resistance and aggression towards NDDC and by implication, operating in conflict ridden environment could make the region perpetually underdeveloped and highly vulnerable to insecurity, poverty and unemployment.

References

- Akiwale, A. A. (2009). Re-engineering the NDDC's master plan: An analytical approach. Retrieved from scribd.com: <https://www.scribd.com/document/96678764...ger-Delta-of-Nigeria>
- Auty, R. (1993). *Sustaining Development in Mineral Economies*. The Resource Curse Thesis, London Routledge
- Belaum, A. (2007). *Organizational development: Changing the way we Manage*. Massachusetts: Bemly Press.
- Collier, P., & Hoeffler, A. (2004). Greed and Grievance in Civil War. *Oxford Economic Papers*, 56, 563-595.
- Echave, J.D., Diez, A., Huber, L., Resesz, B., Ricard, X., & Tanaka, M. (2008). Minciar Conflict to Social. CIES-ACDI-IDRC.
- Ekpenyong, A. (2010). The Oil Economy, Environmental Laws and Human Rights Violation in the Niger Delta Region. Implications and suggested Solutions. *International Journal of Social Policy Research and Development*. Vol.1 (2)
- Eregha, P. B., & Irughe, I. R. (2009). Oil Induced Environmental Degradation in the Nigeria's Niger Delta. The Multiplier Effects. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 11(4), 160-175.
- Eweje, G. (2006). The role of MNEs in community development initiatives in developing countries corporate social responsibility at work in Nigeria and South Africa. *Business & Society*, 45(2), 93-129.
- Folahon, S. O. (2005). *The revolution and community building: Are expectation realistic?* Ibadan: University Press.
- Folaya, C. (1999). Managing the oil proceeds and nation building. *Journal of Management*, 14(2), 66-79.
- Gouldner, A. (1960). The Norm of Reciprocity. *American Sociological Review*, 25(2), 161-178.

- Ganajakaye, S. & Ganajakaye, J. (1993), *Community Empowerment: A Participatory Training Manual on Community Project Development*, New York, PACT Publications.
- Ibaba, S.I. (2011). Amnesty and Peace-Building in the Niger Delta: Addressing the Frustration-Aggression Trap. *Africana: The Niger Delta*, 5(1), 238-269.
- Ibaba, S. I. (2012). *Niger Delta: Constraints and pathways to development*. Ibaba and contributors.
- Jaja, S.A. (2006). *Reinventing the quest: Infrastructural revolution*. Port Harcourt: Pearl Pub.
- Jensen, H.E. (1987). The Theory of Human Nature. *Journal of Economic Issues*, 21(3), 1039-1048.
- Kalaya, S.N. (2005). Financing small-scale business: The demands and supply consideration. *Journal of Economic Development*, 7(11), 143-160.
- Kalaya, S.N. (2006). Organizational culture and innovative practices in the telecommunication Industry. *Journal of Innovation*, 6(2), 47-63.
- Kristiansen, S. (2004). Social networks and business success: The role of subcultures in an African context. *The American Journal of Economics and Sociology*, 63(5), 1149-1171.
- Lasbry, A. (2006). *The past and future of competitive advantage*. Massachusetts: Bemly Press.
- Lohrentz, J.P. (2006). Clarifying the entrepreneurial orientation construct and linking to performance. *Academy of Management Review*, 12(1), 135-172.
- Nareke, L. (2009). Creating new society: The sleeping organizations. *Development Review*, 2(6), 791-823.
- Okolo, P. O. (2014). NDDC, conflict, peace-building and community development in the Niger Delta Region. Retrieved from emerald insight: www.emeraldinsight.com/doi/full/10.1108/09513541011067683
- Oloko, M.M. (2007) *Corporate social responsibility: MNS in unseriousness*, Benin: Omoruyi Press Ltd.
- Unongo, A. (2008), 'The concept of human capital development', *Journal of Political Economy*, 10(2), 281-299.
- Wajda, W., & Angella, T. H. (2012). Social Exchange in a Swedish Work Environment, *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(23), 56-64.
- Willink Commission (1958). Enquiry into the Fears of Minority and the Means of Allaying them. <http://www.adakaboro.org>

APPENDIX 1

Table 4.1: Community Leaders Involvement in Illicit Financial Gains Results in Poor Project Implementation

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
Strongly Agree	666	33.4	33.4
Agree	605	30.3	63.7
Disagree	154	7.7	71.4
Strongly Disagree	93	4.7	76.1
Don't Know	477	24	100
Total	1995	100	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2017

Table 4.2: Community Leaders Involvement in Illicit Financial Gains Results in Poor Monitoring of Contractors

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
Strongly Agree	233	11.7	11.7
Agree	404	20.3	31.9
Disagree	663	33.2	65.2
Strongly Disagree	3219	16.0	81.2
Don't Know	376	18.8	100
Total	1995	100	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2017.

Evaluating the level of transparency in NDDC project development/Design and implementation for community development:

Table 4.3: Needs Assessment Carried out

Respondents	No of respondents	Respondents in %
Yes	500	25.1
No	1481	74.2
No response	14	.7
Total	1995	100
Results of need assessment are communicated to the community		
Yes	407	20.4
No	1572	78.8
Don't know	16	0.8
Total	1995	100
Consensus in project location		
Yes	573	28.7
No	1407	70.5
Don't know	15	0.8
Total	1995	100
There is no conflict between NDDC and community representatives in project Planning, design and execution.		
Yes	649	32.5
No	1331	66.7
Don't know	15	0.8
Total	1995	100

Source: Author's Construction, 2017.

Table 4.4: Community Members Awareness of NDDC Project

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
People are Aware of the Project Benefit	651	32.6	32.6
Only Knew of the Project after its Implementation	586	29.4	62.0
It Involve only Politician	161	8.1	70.1
People were not Aware until its Completion	206	10.3	80.4
Politicians Made us Believe they Brought the Project	374	18.7	99.1
Don't Know	17	.9	100.0
Total	1995	100.0	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2017.

Table 4.5: Elite Involvement in Conception of NDDC Project

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
Strongly Agree	212	10.6	10.6
Agree	520	26.1	36.7
Disagree	504	25.3	62.0
Strongly Disagree	339	17.0	78.9
Don't Know	420	21.1	100
Total	1995	100.0	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2017.

Table 4.6: Community leaders/youths were transparent with NDDC on project execution

Respondents	No of respondents	Respondents in %	Respondents Cumulative %
To a large extent	648	32.5	32.5
Somewhat transparent	592	29.7	62.2
Not transparent	579	29	91.2
Don't know	176	8.8	100
Total	1995	100	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2017

Table 4.7: Community Leaders/Youths were transparent with NDDC

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
To a Large Extent	648	32.5	32.5
Somewhat Transparent	592	29.7	62.2
Not Transparent	176	8.8	71.0
Have no Information on the Level of Transparency	563	28.2	99.2
Don't Know	16	.8	100.0
Total	1995	100.0	

Table 4.8: Community Representatives are very knowledgeable about the Activities of NDDC

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
Strongly Agree	784	39.3	39.3
Agree	543	27.2	66.5
Moderately Agree	182	9.1	75.6
Disagree	292	14.6	90.3
Strongly Disagree	151	7.6	97.8
Don't Know	43	2.2	100.0
Total	1995	100.0	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2017.

Table 4.9: Contractors are in the Habit of Concealing Information from Youths

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
Strongly Agree	342	17.1	17.1
Agree	810	40.6	57.7
Disagree	624	31.3	89.0
Strongly Disagree	186	9.3	98.3
Don't Know	33	1.7	100.0
Total	1995	100.0	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2017.

Table 4.10: Youth Representatives are in the Habit of Misrepresenting the Interest of the Youths

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
Strongly Agree	208	10.4	10.4
Agree	355	17.8	28.2
Disagree	1142	57.2	85.5
Strongly Disagree	233	11.7	97.1
Don't Know	57	2.9	100
Total	1995	100.0	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2017.

Table 4.11: Community Leaders (Elders, Politicians and Youth) Divert Financial Compensation

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
Strongly Agree	178	8.9	8.9
Agree	345	17.3	26.2
Disagree	541	27.1	53.3
Strongly Disagree	461	23.1	76.4
Don't Know	470	23.6	100
Total	1995	100	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2017.

Table 4.13: Pursuit of Illicit Financial Gains from NDDC Staff Leads to Intra-Communal Conflict and Delay of Project Execution

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
Strongly Agree	514	25.8	25.8
Agree	541	27.1	52.9
Disagree	303	15.2	68.1
Strongly Disagree	100	5.0	73.1
Don't Know	537	27	100
Total	1995	100	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2017.

Table 4.14: Conflict between NDDC and Contractors slow Project Implementation

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
Strongly Agree	383	19.2	19.2
Agree	604	30.3	49.5
Disagree	391	19.6	69.1
Strongly Disagree	129	6.5	75.5
Don't Know	488	24.5	100
Total	1995	100.0	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2017.

Table 4.15: NDDC Abandoned Project due to Youth Unrest

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
Strongly Agree	314	15.7	15.7
Agree	301	15.1	30.8
Disagree	821	41.2	72.0
Strongly Disagree	339	17.0	89.0
Don't Know	220	11.1	100
Total	1995	100.0	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2017.

Table 4.16: Poor Conflict Management Skills of Contractors Precipitates Youth Restiveness

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
Strongly Agree	381	19.1	19.1
Agree	654	32.8	51.9
Disagree	326	16.3	68.2
Strongly Disagree	167	8.4	76.6
Don't Know	467	23.5	100
Total	1995	100.0	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2017.

Table 4.17: NDDC Project Outcome is Associated with non-Involvement of Community Member in Project Design

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
Strongly Agree	624	31.3	31.3
Agree	647	32.4	63.7
Disagree	385	19.3	83.0
Strongly Disagree	133	6.7	89.7
Don't Know	206	10.3	100
Total	1995	100.0	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2017.

Table 4.18: Project Quality are Guaranteed if Community Initiate and have Total Buy in of the Project

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
Strongly Agree	984	49.3	49.3
Agree	566	28.4	77.7
Disagree	138	6.9	84.6
Strongly Disagree	94	4.7	89.3
Don't Know	203	10.7	100
Total	1995	100.0	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2017.

Table 4.19: Project will not be abandoned if Community Members are Aware of the Time it was Initiated and do Follow-up

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Respondents in Percentage (%)	Respondents Cumulative %
Strongly Agree	962	48.2	48.2
Agree	560	28.1	76.3
Disagree	152	7.6	83.9
Strongly Disagree	99	5.0	88.9
Don't Know	222	11.1	100
Total	1995	100.0	

Source: Author's Construction, 2017.